

DETECTION OF HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING PVDF SENSOR SIGNALS

J. Kim¹, I. Kim², K. Lee¹, and S.H. Yoon³

¹*Department of Aerospace Engineering, Graduate School, Chungnam National University,
220 Gung-Dong, Yusung-Gu, Daejeon, 305-764, Korea*

²*Department of Aerospace Engineering, Chungnam National University,
220 Gung-Dong, Yusung-Gu, Daejeon, 305-764, Korea*

³*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kumoh National University of Technology,
188 Shinpyung-Dong, Kumi, Korea, 730-710*

SUMMARY: The high-velocity impact such as bird strike, a hailstorm, a small piece of tire or stone during high taxing, and a small piece of engine's fan blade, can cause severe damage to the structures and sub-system in spite of a very small mass. A wide variety of damage modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage in composites can be easily induced by the high-velocity impact. Furthermore, it is often difficult to detect high-velocity impact damage by conventional methods. In this paper, the PVDF(polyvinylidene fluoride) film sensors were used for monitoring impact damage initiation and propagation in composite laminates to illustrate their potential benefit for structural health monitoring. A series of high-velocity impact tests were performed on the air gun impact tester to monitor the stress wave signals due to failure modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage. The wavelet transform and short time Fourier transform are used to decompose PVDF sensor signals in this study. The extent of the damage in each case was examined by means of a conventional ultrasonic C-scan as well as a digital microscope. Test results show that the particular waveform of sensor signals implying the damage initiation and propagation are detected and also there are some relationship among sensor signal, impact energy, and extent of damage. The PVDF sensor signals are shown to carry important information regarding the nature of the high-velocity impact process that can be extracted from the careful signal processing and analysis.

KEYWORDS: high-velocity impact, composite laminates, PVDF sensor, wavelet transform, short time Fourier transform, damage detection.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials in main structures of military and civil aircrafts has increased rapidly because of their considerable advantages over conventional metals in high specific strength and stiffness. However, composite structures are susceptible to damage from low and high-velocity impact, which can produce significant subsurface damages while leaving little or no external visible evidence. Furthermore, it is often difficult to detect impact

damage by conventional methods. Therefore, a health monitoring system for aircraft structures should include the ability to detect impact events and damage they cause[1].

The high-velocity impact such as bird strike, a hailstorm, a small piece of tire or stone during high taxing, and a small piece of engine's fan blade, can cause severe damage to the structures and sub-system in spite of a very small mass. A wide variety of damage modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage in composites can be easily induced by the high-velocity impact. Several techniques for monitoring the low-velocity impact response of composite structure with sensors were proposed by many researchers [2-7]. According to Lih[3], stress wave were strongly influenced by the nature of the force history during impact process. Guo et al. [4] examined that the guided waves due to micro-fracture in composite laminates can be detected by surface mounted sensors and the characteristics of the waves are strongly related to the nature of the fracture process. Sung et al. [5] investigated the characteristics of impact damage of quasi-isotropic laminates using the wavelet analysis. Park et al.[6] showed the possibility for the monitoring of low-velocity impact damage initiation of Gr/Ep panel using piezoelectric thin film sensor. Shih et al. [7] showed the acoustic emission(AE) signal carry important information regarding the nature of the impact process using spectral analysis. The application of localized damage detection and assessment of composite structures, especially high-velocity impact damage is still in its infancy. The alternative method to monitor high-velocity impact damage is to detect stress wave due to impact damage using sensor signals[8,9].

In this paper, the PVDF(polyvinylidene fluoride) film sensors were used for monitoring impact damage initiation and propagation in composite laminates to illustrate their potential benefit for structural health monitoring. A series of high-velocity impact tests were performed on the air gun impact tester to monitor the stress wave signals due to failure modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage. The wavelet transform and short time Fourier transform are used to decompose PVDF sensor signals in this study. The extent of the damage in each case was examined by means of a conventional ultrasonic C-scan as well as a digital microscope. The particular waveform of sensor signals implying the damage initiation and propagation are examined and also relationship among sensor signal, impact energy, and extent of damage are studied.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

High Velocity Impact Test

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 1. The high-velocity air gun impact tester was used to induce impact on composite laminates. The laminate panels were impacted normal to the surface by 10mm diameter spherical steel ball(4.08gr mass) at various impact velocities (energies). It consists of compressor, pressurized air tank, gun barrel, supporting fixture, and laser sensors which are used for measuring steel ball velocity. Two laser sensors(M5L/50, MEL) is mounted at the end of gun barrel and two sensors are located 50mm apart. As the ball crosses the laser sensors, the obtained time duration is used to calculate the velocity of the ball and the kinetic energy of impact. The specimens used in this study are solid laminated panels made of graphite/epoxy unidirectional prepreg (HT145/RS1212, HFG). The panel dimensions were 150×150mm and stacking sequence was [0/90]_{4S}. Four PVDF sensors and two strain gages are attached on the front and rear surface of specimen as shown in Fig. 2. Each specimen was placed on a rigid support and all edges are clamped by a steel fixture. This provides a 100mm by 100mm test area in Fig. 2.

Table 1 presents a summary of the impact test matrix. Nine impact test were conducted on Gr/Ep laminates. The kinetic energy of impact was calculated from the square of impact velocity multiplied by mass of the impactor. By varying the pressure in the system, the velocity of the impactor is controlled. The calibration for pressure-velocity was performed

between 0.2 and 5 kg_f/m². These calibration plot was used to determine pressure setting for each required impact tests. To fire the ball, the chamber is pressurized to a prescribed level and then solenoid valve is released. The sensor signals were digitized by the NI-PXI(National Instrument Co.) data acquisition system and recorded for the further analysis. Two laser sensor signals, 2 strain gage signals, and 4 PVDF sensor signals are simultaneously measured with one laser sensor as trigger signal.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the high-velocity impact pneumatic gun facility

(a) front surface

(b) rear surface

Fig. 2: Dimensions of impact test specimen and the position of sensors on front and rear surface

Table 1: High-velocity impact test matrix

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Pressure(kg _f /cm ²)	0.32	0.56	0.76	1.20	1.60	1.90	2.50	3.30	3.80
Velocity(m/s)	20	49	56	70	84	90	105	111	122
Energy(J)	0.8	4.9	6.4	10	14.4	16.5	22.5	25.1	30.4
Energy ratio	1	6	8	13	18	21	28	31	38
				25	25	25	25		

Piezoelectric Sensors and Signal Processing

The PVDF film sensor(DT1-028, Measurement Specialities) is 15 mm long by 10 mm wide and 28 μm thick. They were mounted on the surface of the laminate with epoxy resin as shown in Fig. 2. When a piezoelectric sensor with effective area A_p and thickness t_p is subjected to strains, ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z the charge developed in the film is given by Q and the corresponding open circuit voltage \bar{V} is then

$$\bar{V} = \frac{Q}{C_p} = \frac{1}{A_p} \int_{A_p} (C_x \epsilon_x + C_y \epsilon_y + C_z \epsilon_z) dA \quad (1)$$

where sensor constant, C_x , C_y , and C_z are defined as

$$C_x = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{31}, \quad C_y = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{32}, \quad \text{and} \quad C_z = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{33}$$

and χ_{33} is the permittivity in the thickness direction, e_{31} , e_{32} , and e_{33} are the piezoelectric constants.

The Fourier transform decompose a signal into its various frequency components. As it uses the sinusoidal basis functions that are localized in frequency only, it loses the transient feature of signals. The short time Fourier transform (STFT) can be candidate for frequency-time analysis. It calculates the local spectral density using windowing techniques to analyze a small section of the signal at a time. However, it is impossible to achieve high resolution in both time and frequency, simultaneously. The STFT is defined as follows:

$$STFT(\tau, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) g(t - \tau) e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (2)$$

where $g(t)$ is short time window and $x(t)$ is signal.

In order to overcome the limitations of harmonic analysis, it has been considered to use the alternative families of orthogonal basis functions called wavelets, instead of sines and cosines. The WT decomposes a signal into a set of basis functions that are localized in both time and frequency[10]. Each wavelet function $\Psi_{a,b}(t)$ is a stretched or narrowed version of a prototype wavelet $\Psi(t)$.

$$\Psi_{a,b}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \Psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right) \quad (3)$$

where a and b are scale and shift parameters, respectively.

As the wavelet basis function is localized in both time and frequency, it can act as multiscale bandpass filters, when convoluted with the signal data. The continuous wavelet transform is defined as follows:

$$W_{\Psi_x}(a, b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) \Psi^*\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right) dt = \langle \Psi(a, b), x(t) \rangle \quad (4)$$

The wavelet transform indicates the similarity between the signal $x(t)$ and the shifts, scales of an elementary function.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sensor Signal Processing

The PVDF sensor signals are recorded during impact and the measured signals with different impact energies are plotted in Figure 3. The PVDF sensor signals show higher frequency signal component relevant to impact damage. The STFT and WT analysis was performed after high bypass filtering process(10KHz). Figure 4 and 5 show results of STFT, WT analysis of PVDF sensor signals for 4 different impact energies. The PVDF sensor signal responds to not only the multiple impact but also stress wave due to the matrix cracking, some delamination, and fiber breakage. Major damage initiation process occurred around 0.5-1.0ms

as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The PVDF sensor signals show higher frequency components above 500kHz for the conditions greater than 10.0J impact energy level. These higher frequency signals may come from stress wave signals due to not only delamination but also some fiber breakage. However, to this time, it is not clear to identify quantitatively the damage modes and severity from the PVDF sensor signals but the frequency spectrum shows that the characteristics of these dominant frequencies are related with the damage mode and impact energy.

Fig. 3: PVDF sensor signals (front, 1-direction)

Fig. 4: Short time Fourier transform for PVDF sensor signals(10KHz high pass filtered)

Fig. 5: Wavelet transform for PVDF sensor signals(10KHz high pass filtered)

Post Impact Damage Assessment

The post impact surface appearance and ultrasonic C-scan for Gr/Ep laminates were shown in Fig. 6. The ultrasonic C-scan was performed using an ultrasonic C-scan system with 5 MHz transducer (Parametric). The C-scan sampling rate was set to 64MHz. C-scan images of amplitude measurements were recorded for each sample. The extent of the internal delaminations can be seen to be much larger than the visible top surface damage in all cases. All of the delaminations were observed not only near the matrix cracks of the bottom surface but also near the top surface. Matrix cracks on the bottom surface were observed for the conditions above the 10J of impact energy. The images and damage area of impacted specimens measured by the ultrasonic C-scan were shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: Digital microscopic image of impacted specimen

(a) 10.0J (area:40 mm²)

(b) 22.5J (area:235 mm²)

(c) 30.4J (area:373 mm²)

Fig. 7: Ultrasonic C-scan image and damage area of impacted specimen

CONCLUSIONS

An impact monitoring system based on the use of a discrete number of sensor requires an efficient signal process algorithm that can detect impact damage from the sensor signal. The damage detection method for the damage-induced high-velocity impact of graphite/epoxy laminates using PVDF film sensor signals were examined. Both impact testing and signal processing work were conducted. The experimental examination to detect impact damage led to the following conclusions:

- 1) It is found that PVDF film sensor can be used to detect high-velocity impact damage because sensor signals are sensitive to not only vibrational mode but also stress waves due to impact damage.
- 2) Signal processing of PVDF sensor signal shows the possibility of correlating the extent of impact damage, failure mode with sensor signal.

It is necessary to investigate the characteristic of damage signals for each failure mode and extent during impact process and correlate the PVDF sensor signals with acoustic emission signals.

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REFERENCES

1. Lincoln, J.W., "USAF Experience in the Qualification of Composite Structures", *Composite Structures; Theory and Practice*, ASTM STP 1383, 2000, pp. 3-11.
2. Kim, I. and Hahn, H. T., "Prediction of Low-Energy Impact Based on Piezoelectric Sensor Signals", *ASME*, AD-Vol.35, 1993, pp. 433-439.
3. Lih, S. S and Mal, A.K., "Response of Multilayered Composite Laminates to Dynamic Surface Loads", *Composites: Part B*, 27B, 1996, pp. 633-644.
4. Guo D., Mal, A.K., and Ono, K., "Wave Theory of Acoustic Emission in Composite Laminates", *Journal of Acoustic Emission*, 1996, 14, pp. 19-46.

5. Sung, D. U., Oh, J. H., Kim, C. G., and Hong, C. S., "Impact Damage Detection of Smart Composite Laminates Using Wavelet Transform", *Journal of the Korean Society for Composite Materials*, Vol.13, No.1, 2000, pp. 40-49.
6. Shih, J.H. and Mal, A.K., "Acoustic Emission from Impact Damage in Cross-ply Composites", *Proceedings of Structural Health Monitoring*, 2000, pp. 209-217.
7. Park, C. Y., I. Kim, and Y. S. Lee., "Monitoring of Low-velocity Impact Damage Initiation of Gr/Ep Panel Using Piezoelectric Thin Film Sensor", *Journal of the Korean Society for Composite Materials*, Vol.15, No.2, 2002, pp.11-17.
8. Okafor, A.C., Otieno, Dutta, A.W., and Rao, A. V.S. "Detection and Characterization of High-Velocity Impact Damage in Advanced Composite Plates Using Multi-sensing Techniques", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 54, 2001, pp. 289-297.
9. Tanabe, Y. and Aoki, M., "Stress and Strain Measurements in Carbon-Related Materials Impacted by a High-Velocity Steel Sphere", *Int. J. Impact Engineering*, Vol. 28, 2001, pp. 1045-1059.
10. Newland, D.E. *Random Vibrations, Spectral and Wavelet Analysis*, Longman Scientific & Technical, 1993.